

Facing power sector deficits in Ecuador

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- Keywords

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Executive Summary

This study explores the potential for expanding Ecuador's power sector through the strategic deployment of small-scale renewable energy plants across diverse locations, addressing the country's reliance on hydropower and the need to mitigate electricity deficits currently compensated by costly imports. Utilizing the Energy Access Explorer tool for integrated energy planning, the research identifies 24 prime sites for hydropower projects that avoid ecological sensitivities, alongside significant solar and wind energy potential in key urban and mountainous regions. The findings highlight the viability of leveraging Ecuador's rich geographical diversity, including its active volcanoes and consistent wave patterns, to explore geothermal and wave energy sources. The necessity of conducting comprehensive Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) before project initiation is emphasized to ensure ecological preservation. Despite promising opportunities for enhancing energy self-sufficiency and transitioning towards a more sustainable energy mix, the study acknowledges challenges such as data scarcity, climate change impacts, and the critical need for political support in realizing the full potential of renewable energy projects in Ecuador. This holistic approach to renewable energy expansion presents a pathway to reducing dependency on imported energy, fostering economic savings, and contributing to environmental sustainability.

1. Introduction

Ecuador is the most densely populated country in South America (63 people/km²) (INEC 2024), located on the east Pacific Ocean at the Equator. It has over 18 million people in 4 regions; mountain range, coast, amazon region, and the Galapagos Islands. Since 2017,

there have been no new investment to expand the power sector supply. According to the latest existing data (2022), the 61.2% is renewable energy and 38.7% is not renewable, reaching a nominal power of 8871 MW. The majority comes from hydropower (58%), thermoelectric power plants run by internal combustion engines (ICE) (23%), and turbogas power plants (11%) (MEM 2022) (See Figure 1).

On the other hand, the power generation reaches 3.3 PWh, and it is equally shared as the power distribution. However, there is some generation deficit cover by imports from Colombia and Peru (757 GWh) (MEM 2022). This electricity is very expensive, thus invest in new power plants is better in terms of cost-benefit.

Furthermore, most of hydropower plants are run-of river, having reservations for a few hours only. Additionally, the largest hydropower plant has 1500 MW of power, however in dry season at the end of the year, it cannot generate what is need it to cover the electricity demand. Therefore, at this time of the year comes the imports of electricity, thus I possible solution encompass new power plants in various location. They could be rather small and better distributed. This work aims to present suitable locations to expand the power sector supply to fill the electricity deficit in the country. To do this, the Energy Access Explorer tool allows us for integrated and inclusive energy planning to support decision-making in the power sector. Therefore, this report follows this order; Section 2 describes the methodology employed; Section 3 presents results and discussion; finally, conclusions of this study as well as some recommendations in Section 4.

Figure 1: Generation and capacity of the power sector by technology

2. Methodology

The Energy Access Explorer (EAE) is an online open source (Mentis et al. 2019), interactive, geospatial platform. This tool enables clean energy entrepreneurs, energy

planners, donors, and development-oriented institutions to identify high priority areas where energy access can be expanded. Thus, the EAE tool was used to address possible locations to expand the energy supply, since this tool makes it possible to locate suitable areas with high energy potential and cross-reference information with other geospatial variables to enrich the analysis.

The EAE has developed the energy access potential index to facilitate the expansion of energy access in some region. This index includes two more indexes; the supply index, which integrates supply variables such as global horizontal irradiation, distance to the distribution lines, wind speed, among others; and the demand index that integrate variables such as population density, poverty rates, among others. These indexes apply weighing factors and normalized data ([Mentis et al. 2019](#)).

The information comes from various sources. Thus, it was uploaded all relevant datasets, from the supply, demand side, and under the category of others. From the supply side, there are power plants, transmission network, distribution lines ([SNI 2024](#)), resources information such as wind speed and global horizontal irradiation come from global atlas open source ([World Bank 2024a, 2024b](#)). From the demand side, there are productive uses such as public markets, schools, and healthcare facilities ([OpenStreetMap 2024b, 2024a, 2024c](#)), demographic variables such as population density and relative wealth index come from ([WorldPop 2024](#); [Meta 2024](#)). Under the group of other datasets, there are the administrative boundaries ([INEC, 2024](#)) and environmental variables such as forest, protected areas, and wetlands ([SNI, 2024](#)).

Armed with comprehensive data and leveraging the capabilities of EAE, multiple sites were identified for the implementation of solar, wind, and hydroelectric energy projects. A multi-criteria analysis, incorporating overlays and filters within the EAE platform, facilitated the identification of areas with significant potential for energy access, aimed at augmenting the supply in the power sector. The filters used for wind speed was over 6 m/s, for global solar irradiation over 1660 kWh/m², and the proximity in kilometres for the distribution lines equal or less than 2 km.

These selected sites are characterized by their high potential for energy access and their exclusion from protected zones. It is fundamentally presumed that there exists a political inclination and financial resources dedicated to investing in the expansion of the power sector, focusing on the establishment of comparatively small-scale renewable energy installations.

3. Results and discussion (600 – 1000)

Once the methodology is applied, there are multiple location for wind, solar, and hydro energy projects with high resources potential as well as high energy access potential index.

Since most of the Ecuadorian electricity comes primarily from hydropower plants, this renewable energy is key to replace non-renewables in the power sector. Last hydropower plants built are large and run-of-river power plants, moreover, these plants are mainly located on the south of the country, which is a zone that experiences droughts at the end of the year, and no new project has been implemented since 2017.

Figure 2: Potential sites to implement reservoir hydropower plants

Therefore, it is uppermost important to think in rather small power plants better distributed across the country. Thus, there are 24 locations with high hydropower potential that do not overlap with wetlands, protected forest, protected areas, and biosphere reserves, moreover, all rivers considered have high flow. These power plants are thinking to be reservoir hydropower plants to diversify the current type of hydropower plants and at the same time to increase the reservoir hours from 8 hours to maybe a day or two. Furthermore, these hydropower plants will be small and better distributed throughout the country, avoiding climate-related inconveniences as much as possible (See Figure 2).

Regarding solar energy, there are multiple cities mainly on the mountain range with high solar energy potential (over 1660 kWh/m²). These cities also have high and medium high energy access potential index such as, Tulcan, Ibarra, Montufar, Atuntaqui, Cotacachi, Quito, Ambato, Pelileo, Riobamba, Cañar, Azogues, Cuenca, Loja. There is some high energy access potential in cities on the coast as well such as, Guayaquil, Santa Elena. These are the main cities in the country, thus it could be an opportunity to promote renewables for housing. For example, recently there is new legislation to promote the use of renewable energy in homes. This legislation allows electricity generated in homes to be

deducted from the electricity bill. This could be a good start in promoting renewables for housing (See Figure 3).

Figure 3: Solar energy potential and energy access potential

Figure 4: Wind energy potential and energy access potential

In the context of wind energy, the mountain ranges emerge as areas of significant potential, hosting 19 sites with optimal conditions for wind energy generation, complemented by accessible energy prospects in four cities: Loja (17 sites), Cañar, Latacunga, and Pelileo (See Figure 4). Notably, Loja already benefits from an operational wind power facility, with ongoing studies aimed at its expansion. This presents an opportunity for local and national governments, alongside energy cooperation agencies, to strategize for the augmentation of existing wind energy projects and the initiation of new ventures.

The construction of small-scale renewable power plants stands as a pragmatic approach, not solely due to the abundant energy potential but also considering the cost-effectiveness over medium to long-term horizons. Presently, the electricity shortfall is mitigated through imports from Colombia and Peru, which incur costs significantly higher than domestic production. Hence, the establishment of new small-scale renewable power plants could effectively bridge the electricity deficit, fostering an environment of energy surplus conducive to exporting electricity.

Furthermore, the exploration of alternative renewable energy sources, such as geothermal and wave energy, holds promise, particularly given Ecuador's geographical endowments of active volcanoes and consistent, directional waves ([Portilla et al. 2020](#)). Preliminary investigations into geothermal energy prospects in the Galapagos Islands and the mountain ranges, as well as wave energy potential in the Galapagos, underscore the diversified renewable energy portfolio that Ecuador could develop.

However, the initiation of renewable energy projects is invariably accompanied by environmental considerations. Prior to project commencement, a thorough Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is imperative, with a focus on identifying and mitigating potential impacts on vulnerable ecological zones, species at risk, erosion-prone areas, and crucial water sources.

This study, while comprehensive, acknowledges certain limitations, particularly concerning data availability in some regions, potential climate variability leading to droughts and floods, and, most critically, the uncertainty surrounding political commitment to renewable energy initiatives. These factors collectively underscore the complexities and challenges inherent in advancing Ecuador's renewable energy landscape.

5. Conclusion

The application of the methodology reveals numerous potential sites across Ecuador for wind, solar, and hydro energy projects, each exhibiting high resource potential and energy access indices. Given the country's reliance on hydropower, diversification into smaller,

geographically dispersed renewable energy plants is imperative. The identification of 24 hydropower sites outside critical ecological zones, with high-flow rivers, suggests a strategic shift towards small reservoir hydropower plants to enhance storage capacity and mitigate climate-related risks.

The mountain region, along with key urban centers, show significant solar energy potential, aligning with recent legislative efforts to promote residential renewable energy use. This presents an opportunity to reduce dependence on imported energy, which is costlier than domestic production, and to foster a self-sustaining energy model that could potentially lead to an energy surplus.

Wind energy also emerges as a viable option, particularly in the mountain ranges and specific cities on the south of the country, like Loja, which could be expanded or replicated. The strategic development of small-scale renewable plants could address the current electricity deficit and contribute to a more sustainable and resilient energy sector.

However, the initiation of such projects must be preceded by comprehensive Environmental Impact Assessments to safeguard ecological zones. Despite promising prospects, challenges such as data limitations, climate variability, and uncertain political support for renewable initiatives pose significant hurdles to the realization of Ecuador's renewable energy potential.

As recommendation, the should think more in small-scale renewable power plants netter distributed throughout the country. The government should also keep promoting renewable energy for housing. Regarding the EAE tool, deploy all datasets to the stage level in order that public in general have access to this tool. Also, keep access and contact to upload useful information of our respective countries.

For future Work, first, update the current data related to power plants and distribution lines, apply the OnSSET model for electrification, and then do a cost-benefit analysis and present these insights to get feedback from stakeholders or experts in the field.

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